

Metrics Summary Tables

Part 1: Projects P18-P67

Metrics	P18-storybook	P20-firebase	P28-react-dev	P29-esbuild-w	P36-apollo	P38-opentel	P4-prisma-c	P40-bootstrap	P47-firebase-d	P50-esbuild-l	P54-prettier	P56-puppeteer	P59-playwright-c	P67-redux	P70-chart	P74-stripe	P76-sass
CC μ / σ	4.1/22.2	3.2/15.4	0/0	4.5/18.5	3.5/5.2	2.5/3.3	3/4.8	2.8/2.9	3.2/15.4	4.8/8.1	4.3/27	2.7/4.5	4.5/9.2	4.5/32.2	3.4/3.3	2.9/4.8	2/2.4
CBO μ / σ	0.2/0.6	0.3/0.9	0/0	0.5/0.9	0.5/0.7	0.3/0.7	0.7/1.1	0.2/0.7	0.3/0.7	0/0	0/0	0.6/1	0.9/1.3	0/0	0.2/0.5	0.1/0.4	1.1/4.3
Classes/File μ / σ	0.1/1	0.5/2.5	0.1/0.5	0.3/1.7	0.1/0.4	0.3/0.7	0.1/0.5	0.4/2.3	0.5/2.5	0.1/0.5	0.2/0.8	0.4/0.9	0.4/1.3	0/0.1	0.1/0.3	0.1/0.6	0.5/0.5
Imports/File μ / σ	3/3.5	5/5.4	0/0	2/4.2	3.6/3.8	3.1/3.2	2.7/3	2.8/2.6	5/5.4	3.3/2.8	0.5/1.7	4.1/4.5	3.6/4.7	2.3/2.5	0.5/1.5	1/3.5	5.6/4.9

Table 1: Software metrics summary (Part 1/2): Projects P18-P76

Part 2: Projects P77-P99

Metrics	P77-gcloud-f	P78-webpack	P79-highlight	P8-prisma	P80-sentry	P83-fp-ts	P84-html-min	P85-msw	P86-luxon	P89-rxjs	P90-faker	P92-moment	P95-react-r	P96-zod	P97-playwright	P98-mongodb	P99-aws-s3
CC μ / σ	3.2/2.8	6.2/21.5	0/0	3/4.8	3.6/4.5	1.5/1.3	6.6/15.2	0/0	3/5.6	2.7/3.8	2.1/2.6	5.1/8.2	4.8/13	3.8/8	4.5/9.2	5.7/8	4.1/29.7
CBO μ / σ	0.1/0.5	0.3/0.7	0/0	0.7/1.1	0.1/0.3	0/0	0/0	0/0	0.8/1.3	0.3/0.8	0/0	0/0	0/0	0.3/1	0.9/1.3	0.5/1.6	0/0
Classes/File μ / σ	1/2.6	0.1/2.3	0/0.2	0.1/0.5	0.1/1.4	0/0.1	0.3/0.7	0.1/0.3	0.3/1	0.1/0.6	0/0.2	0/0	0/0.2	0.2/2.1	0.4/1.3	0.3/1.6	0.4/1
Imports/File μ / σ	5.8/5.6	1.1/5	0/0	2.7/3	2.5/2.5	7.9/10.2	4.4/3.4	0/0	2.1/2.4	2.9/2.4	1.4/3.4	1.8/2.1	2.9/3.3	2.3/1.4	3.6/4.7	3/4.6	4.2/7.1

Table 2: Software metrics summary (Part 2/2): Projects P77-P99

Cyclomatic Complexity Distribution

Bar chart showing mean cyclomatic complexity with error bars representing standard deviation across all 34 projects. This metric quantifies code complexity through decision points and control flow structures.

Figure 1: Mean cyclomatic complexity with standard deviation error bars

Coupling Between Objects (CBO)

Bar chart displaying CBO mean values with standard deviation. CBO measures class-level coupling by counting distinct classes each class depends upon, derived from Chidamber-Kemerer metrics suite.

Figure 2: CBO mean values with standard deviation error bars

Imports per File Distribution

Bar chart showing mean number of imports per file with standard deviation. This metric represents module fan-out, quantifying external dependencies at the file level.

Figure 3: Mean imports per file with standard deviation error bars

Classes per File Distribution

Bar chart displaying mean number of classes per file with standard deviation. This metric quantifies object-oriented design density and class organization patterns across projects.

Figure 4: Mean classes per file with standard deviation error bars

File Statistics Comparison

Stacked bar chart comparing total files, TypeScript files, and JavaScript files across projects. This provides insight into codebase size and language composition.

Figure 5: File composition by type across all projects

Error Rate Analysis

Grouped bar chart displaying error counts by category (file, parse, metric, traverse) per project. This metric indicates analysis robustness and potential code quality issues.

Figure 6: Error distribution by category across projects

Maximum Cyclomatic Complexity

Bar chart showing maximum cyclomatic complexity value found in each project. High values indicate presence of highly complex functions requiring refactoring attention.

Figure 7: Maximum cyclomatic complexity per project

Total Functions Count

Bar chart displaying total number of functions analyzed per project. This metric correlates with codebase size and functional decomposition.

Figure 8: Total function count across projects

Complexity Distribution Histogram

Histogram showing distribution of mean cyclomatic complexity values across all projects. Groups projects into complexity ranges to identify architectural patterns.

Figure 9: Distribution of mean cyclomatic complexity across projects

Error Analysis by Category

Stacked bar chart showing error distribution by type (file, parse, traverse) per project. Projects excluded: P28, P79, P85 (metrics unavailable), P99 (extreme outlier with 57619 file errors).

Figure 10: Error distribution by category (P99-aws-sdk-client-s3 excluded due to 57619 file errors)

File Type Distribution Heatmap

Comparison of TypeScript vs JavaScript file counts across projects. Shows technology stack preferences and migration patterns.

Figure 11: TypeScript vs JavaScript file distribution across projects

Top 10 Most Complex Functions

Horizontal bar chart displaying the most complex individual functions across all projects. Extreme complexity values (>2000) indicate potential code generation or bundled artifacts.

Figure 12: Top 10 most complex functions with their cyclomatic complexity values

Complexity vs Project Size Scatter Plot

Scatter plot correlating average cyclomatic complexity with total function count. Identifies large complex projects vs small focused libraries.

Figure 13: Relationship between project size (total functions) and average complexity